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PFAS Optical Detection Approach in Mar2Protect

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Mar2Protect project is a European project, funded by the European Union that aims to give a holistic approach for the water protection. This project has several demsites selected due to climatic conditions, water sources and pollution type. One of the objectives is to monitor contaminants relevant to each demsite and the per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are one of the contaminants under study. PFAS are a group of fluorinated, organic compounds with stable carbon-fluoride bonds [1]. The most common detection methods are laboratorial methods with high associated costs, time-consuming and unsuitable for in-situ analysis. It is therefore important to develop sensors for the detection and real-time monitoring of PFAS that can allow quick analysis and simple operation [2]. Optical sensors can be a suitable approach for in-situ monitoring since it allows compactness, lightweight, immunity to electromagnetic interference and also multiplexing capabilities [3]. In this work, the Mar2Protect approach for the detection and monitoring of PFAS will be shown. The proposed approach is a combination between a selective layer developed by FCT NOVA and an optical sensor setup developed by IT. Considerations for the upscaling from the laboratory to the field will also be shown, aiming the sensor implementation to one of the project demsites.

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References

- [1] Thompson D., Zolfigol N., Xia Z., Lei Y., Recent progress in per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) sensing: A critical mini-review, *Sens. Actuators Rep.*, **2024**, 7 (100189), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snr.2024.100189>.
- [2] Rodriguez K.L., Hwang J.H., Esfahani A.R., Sadmani A.H.M.A., Lee W.H., Recent developments of PFAS-detecting sensors and future direction: A review. *Micromachines (Basel)*, **2020**, 11 (667), 1-23, <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi11070667>.
- [3] Pires Duarte D. A., Nogueira R. N., Billo L., *Optical Fiber Sensing Principles. Plastic Optical Fiber Sensors, Science Technology and Applications*, CRC Press, **2019**, 67–91, <https://doi.org/10.1201/b22357-3>.

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